

Consumer Satisfaction and Service Quality in Commercial Transportation: An Expedition of SERVQUAL Dimensions

Author's Details: Yuvaraja Seegodu Eshwarappa,
Islington College, London Metropolitan University (UK), and Kathmandu, Nepal

Abstract:

Yes, there is no readymade marketing strategy for any goods and services in the world of business! Marketers must craft the distinct marketing strategies for every product. Nonetheless the one and only ultimate objective of the strategies will be to satisfy the customers. When we consider the strategies for services, it is much stiffer and riskier than goods. It is harder in every aspects of marketing. But fairly, it is proven in many studies that the strong service quality can lead to higher consumer satisfaction from services. Even if we believe that there is a strong relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction, there are plenty of slipups to understand the concept of service quality itself. So it is very clear at this point to identify the industry and products wide customer satisfaction models with respect to service quality. In this research paper, an attempt has been made to identify the relationship model between service quality and consumer satisfaction for transportation industry with respect to Nepal's private transportation industry, which may provide a regression model for customer satisfaction. The proposed regression model is to afford a mathematical equation for consumer satisfaction with respect to service quality and its determinants. The results will aid both the marketers and researchers for better understanding of the service quality in transportation industry and a mathematical tool to control the level of satisfaction by directing service quality.

Index Terms: Customer Satisfaction, Service Quality, SERVQUAL, Transportation Industry, Services Marketing

Introduction:

There are 100's of studies have been conducted to find out the factors of service quality which lead to higher consumer satisfaction but it is not convincing for most of the researchers and marketers. The notable measurement instrument for service quality is the SERVQUAL method which has been used since 1988, also had to face many criticisms. Consumer satisfaction is the one gadget which every marketers and entrepreneurs will die to have for their businesses. But it is the myth to many of them to understand and activate it. Transportation companies are also not exempted. The transportation in Nepal is not easy as we think from other places because of its geographical obstacles. Government is trying to improve the transportation infrastructure, but not hard and lack in political willingness. Recently the public transportation system has been opened up for city limits but not for inter cities.

There was system and institution called NTBS, Nepal Trolley Bus Service which ended up its journey in 2008 due to under cost management and political changes. NTBS started in 1975 and its interurban line was connecting Kathmandu and the satellite towns, doing very well in its initial stages. But the management of the trolley bus service faced a series of hostile government bureaucracy incidents and led to overstaffing and incurred huge losses in their cost sheet. More over the NTBS was under NTC, Nepal Transportation Corporation which comes under government bureaucracy ended up with the revenue which was not enough to pay its staff and electricity. (My Republica, 2012) As I experienced, bus transportation is the main source of public transportation in Nepal. But most of the bus transportation is managed by private companies. The government also provides transportation facility which has the distinctive blue and white buses.

The government service is not available to Far East and Far West due to difficult terrain and extreme weather conditions.

The blue and white buses are usually shabby, ill managed and unscheduled. Government buses are popularly called as Sajha Yatayat. There are literally dozens of private bus companies. Long distance buses must be booked in advance with the Sajha buses. There are express minibuses which travel day and night in the long routs which makes quite scheduled for any passengers. It is always preferable to travel in day light because of countryside view and spectacular rivers, hills, mountains and even roads as well. More than everything it is safer than night travel due to unexpected cuts and turnouts in the roads. Hours of sleep would also be given in night travel which any way is not enough.

Definitely local transport using local buses no way preferable for the tourists due to various inconveniences. Maoist activities have been increased in recent past which caused many more check points by Nepal's military troops. Many of the long routs have been considerably slowed down due to these check points and lot of irritation for the tourists. Literally the passengers have to get down and walking through check points for detailed checkup which will cause extreme inconvenient for the passengers. Tourists are normally exempt and can stay on the bus. Number of these kind of check points definitely extends the travel time and more hectic for the tourists a well as passengers (Lonely Planet, 2014).

Private transportation in Nepal is quite exciting due to good view of mountains, hills and plains in reasonably well maintained buses. It is also excited to think twice about the life of the people which we could see by land drive, the hill tops villages, small brooks and rivers which cuts the roads for many hill top villages. Some of the well-known bus transportation companies such as Green Line proposes that the travel in private buses are quite safe, scheduled and at the international standards.

But still the transportation industry in Nepal has not been exploited in its full strength and require as many as studies to boost up the revenue for the companies. In this research paper, there is an attempt to identify the satisfaction level of

the consumers in terms of the service quality to understand and upgrade the level of service quality by the government and private transportation companies.

Literature review:

In most of the studies it has been proven that the customer satisfaction from services and service quality have the stronger relationship. But it differs in the regression models. Transaction specific model and SERVQUAL model has its own merits and demerits to understand the influence of service quality and customer satisfaction. (Dabholkar, 1993) However it has been recently argued that the "Satisfaction is generally viewed as a broader concept but not merely a transaction specific and service quality is a component of satisfaction" (Valarie A. Zeithaml, 2003).

Consumer Satisfaction:

Consumer satisfaction is a key aspect in realization of consumer's requirements for upcoming consumption (Mittal, 2001). Moreover, the pleased consumers will possibly convert to others about their decent experiences. This element, particularly in the Middle Eastern cultures, where the social & cultural life has been formed in a manner that societal communication with other people improves the society, is more important (Naseer, 2002). Even though satisfaction has been well-defined as the difference between anticipation and enactment, but there are dissimilarities between quality and satisfaction. For example, Parasuraman (Parasuraman, 1988) say that satisfaction is a conclusion made after experience while quality is not the same.

On the other hand, in satisfaction literature, expectations for goods is "would", while in service quality literature, expectations for goods is "should". Cadotte & Turgeon (Cadotte, 1988) have introduced another group of elements known as neutral factors.

Besides, Liljander & Strandvik (1993) say that experience is not needed for assessing service quality, and service can be evaluated on the basis of the facts about service provider, while satisfaction is an inner view, caused from customer's own experience from the service. (Churchill, 1982) Finally, numerous researches have been done on the relation between service quality and satisfaction: findings of some of these investigates show that satisfaction results in service quality (Parasuraman et al., 1988). Also, the research conducted by Sureshchandar et al. (2002) shows that, there is a two-way relation between satisfaction and service quality. (Carman, 1990)

SERVQUAL Dimensions:

Quality is a multi-dimensional wonder. Thus, attainment of the service quality without distinguishing the important aspects of quality is difficult. In his discussion of service quality, Gronroos (C, 2000) refers to three proportions of output technical quality, service performance quality, & organization's mental picture. Also, Lehtinen have referred to dimensions of physical quality, interactive quality, & organizational quality as three dimensions of service quality. Although these attempts have had a major role in division of service quality into process quality and output quality, but they lack enough details. On this basis, Zeithaml et al.

(1996) have referred to ten dimensions of service quality in their primary researches. Thus, they combined these dimensions and applied the fivefold dimension of Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, Empathy and Tangibles as a basis for making a tool for testing the service quality, known as SERVQUAL. In their researches, they emphasize that SERVQUAL is a lasting and reliable scale of service quality. In my research, SERVQUAL has been used for designing questions related to service quality, Gremler and Brown's tool (Gremler, 1996) for evaluating the loyalty, and for customer satisfaction evaluation, a tool offered by Bitner and Hubbert (1994) has been used.

Conceptual Research Framework:

As primary research is required to understand the customer satisfaction and service quality, the data have been collected through questionnaire from 134 frequent customers from three different transportation companies. Sample size has been estimated by considering the population numbers estimating the average number of passengers per week. All male and female, different aged, educated and all level of income passengers who travel from Kathmandu to other urban cities have been targeted for the data collection.

Convenient sampling technique has been used to draw the responses. Overall research paper has been written by primary sources such as questionnaire and direct interview. Secondary resources such as books, journals and internet sources are also have been used to withdraw the results. Collected data have been processed by using both descriptive and inferential statistical tools. Data have been measured in nominal, ordinal as well as scale levels and analysed using SPSS. Research based on this framework has been smeared to the transportation industry by various researchers and marketers, who created many other models with nearly encouraging results. Although the SERVQUAL framework has been trailed with some interest in various service businesses, empirical support for the submitted structure has not continuously been promising.

So based on the hypothesis, I am trying to create a typical model for Nepal's transportation industry basically to civil transportation so that it can be utilized as a basis for further research and management purpose (Andaleeb, 2006). A set of 134 consumers have been interviewed with a questionnaire and analysed the data using various statistical tools to test the results. The correlation technique has been used to identify the relationship between each factors with the level of satisfaction and regression technique has been used to find the level of correlation between the factors.

In questionnaire, SERVQUAL dimensions have been converted into different factors such as convenience, reliability, assurance, comfort, cleanliness, comfort in excursions and helpfulness of the employees for better data collection. Different hypothesis testing methods have been used based on the scale of measurements for different factors for reliability test of the results.

The hypothesis for the study is $\Omega 1$ i.e.

H1 – There is no significant relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction

H0 – There is a significant relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction

Consumer Satisfaction (μ) depends on Service Quality (β)

$$f(\mu) = a_0 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (\beta_n + \beta_{n+1})$$

Where a_0 is constant, Tangibles – $\beta 1$, Responsiveness – $\beta 2$, Reliability – $\beta 3$, Empathy – $\beta 4$ And Assurance – $\beta 5$

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (\beta_n + \beta_{n+1}) \quad [\text{Perceived Values}]$$

$\beta 1$ (Tangibles) – Cleanliness (ϵb)

$\beta 2$ (Responsiveness) – Helpfulness (ϵc)

$\beta 3$ (Reliability) – Excursions (ϵd) and Expertise

$\beta 4$ (Empathy) – Convenience (ϵf)

$\beta 5$ (Assurance) – Comfort (ϵa) and Safety (ϵg)

Research Analysis:

To identify the level of influence by the dimensions of SERVQUAL to consumer satisfaction, a simple mathematical equation can help for both marketers and researchers. Above conceptual framework will be expressed with gradients attached to dimensions of SERVQUAL which can be predicted the level of consumer satisfaction. Gradient depends on the population view on service quality which is completely depends on various environmental factors.

A sample of 134 passengers have been asked for their opinion which can predict the population opinion on service quality and consumer satisfaction. 31.5% of male and 68.5% of female passengers have been interviewed which has been chosen through random sampling.

There were 3% of the passengers who did not specify their gender but gave their opinions. 25.6% and 72.1% of single and married passengers have been interviewed but 2.3 of passengers have not specified their marital status.

Samples are aged less than 20, 20-29, 30-39, 40-49, 50 & above and 10.3%, 9.5%, 14.3%, 26.2% and 39.7% of each have been interviewed respectively. Out of 134 passengers, 23.3% of high school, 26.4% of +2 college, 16.3% of diploma, 17.8% of degree and 16.3% of post graduates have been interviewed.

Their monthly income has been classified as less than 20000, 20000 to 39999, 40000 to 59999, 60000 to 79999 and 80000 & above and 42.7%, 32.5%, 16.2%, 4.3% and 4.3% have been given their opinions respectively.

Estimation at 95% confidence level					
Factors evaluation on 7 rating Likert scale				Statistic	Std. Error
1. Departure location is convenient	Sample Mean			3.61	.146
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound		3.32	
		Upper Bound		3.90	
2. Bus journey is safe	Sample Mean			3.56	.150
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound		3.26	
		Upper Bound		3.86	
3. Company is expert in conducting transportation	Sample Mean			4.35	.154
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound		4.05	
		Upper Bound		4.66	
4. Comfort	Sample Mean			3.34	.133
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound		3.07	
		Upper Bound		3.60	
5. Cleanliness	Sample Mean			2.93	.144
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound		2.64	
		Upper Bound		3.21	
6. Excursions	Sample Mean			3.84	.137
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound		3.56	
		Upper Bound		4.11	
7. Staffs Responsiveness	Sample Mean			3.97	.161
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound		3.65	
		Upper Bound		4.29	
8. Overall Satisfaction	Sample Mean			4.23	.155
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound		3.92	
		Upper Bound		4.54	

The collected data from samples have been estimated at 95% confidence level and the factors have been rated as per Likert scale. As per the estimation the passengers have the following satisfaction level in each category. As above table shows the tangibles have least satisfied level and reliability and assurance have high satisfied level among five dimensions. But overall the satisfaction level is not up to the industry standard.

Research Results:

The correlation between the factors of service quality and consumer satisfaction has been analysed through sample’s data with respect to transportation industry as follows,

Correlation between overall satisfaction and service quality factors		
Service Quality Factors	Method of Correlation	Correlation Score
1. Staffs Responsiveness	Pearson Correlation	.099**
2. Company is expert in conducting transportation	Pearson Correlation	.380**
3. Excursions	Pearson Correlation	.500**
4. Departure location is convenient	Pearson Correlation	.658**
5. Bus journey is safe	Pearson Correlation	.484**
6. Comfort	Pearson Correlation	.464**

As above table shows the different level of correlation with respect to overall satisfaction which every factor has positive correlation. Which is proven again that all the dimensions of the SERVQUAL method have positive correlation with consumer satisfaction. Only responsiveness factor has low correlation which expresses the customer does not mind with the helpfulness of the staff. A low interaction during the journey could be the reason for this attitude. (Everitt-Bryant, 1996) The factors such as

safety, expertise and comfort level has moderate correlation with consumer satisfaction. Remaining factors such as excursions and departure location has high correlation with overall satisfaction. Above analysis shows that the transportation industry in Nepal has much depends on the departure location or comfort ability followed by safety, comfort, expertise and excursions ability of the transportation companies. Which also expresses the least dependency on staff responsiveness.

Ω1 has been tested by one sample T test and found that, it is statistically significant and we must reject the null hypothesis. The following results found in SPSS one sample T test analysis,

SERVQUAL Factors	Hypothesis Testing	Test Results
1. Cleanliness	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
2. Staffs Responsiveness	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002
3. Expertise	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
4. Excursions	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
5. Departure location	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
6. Bus journey is safe	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Based on the above results the regression analysis has been done in forward method to identify the important factor which led to customer satisfaction as follows,

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.702	.278		6.127	.000
	1. Departure location is convenient	.700	.070	.658	10.05	.000

a. Dependent Variable: 4. Overall Satisfaction 1=completely disagree, 7=completely agree

The above table shows that the convenient in departure location which comes under empathy has the most influencing level to consumer satisfaction. Other excluded variables under forward method as follows,

Excluded Variables ^a						
Model		Beta In	t	Sig.	Partial Correlation	Collinearity Statistics
						Tolerance
1	5. Comfort	-.003b	-.037	.970	-.003	.499
	7. Excursion is organised	.046b	.486	.627	.042	.473
	2. Bus journey is safe	.048b	.517	.606	.045	.511
	3. Company is expert in conducting transportation	-.081b	-.945	.346	-.082	.580

a. Dependent Variable: 4. Overall Satisfaction 1=completely disagree, 7=completely agree
 b. Predictors in the Model: (Constant), 1. Departure location is convenient 1=completely disagree, 7=completely agree

As per the regression analysis results, $f(\mu) = a_0 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty}(\beta_n + \beta_{n+1})$ can be viewed as follows,

$$f(\mu) = 1.702 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [(0.7(\text{Empathy}) + .048(\text{Assurance}) - 0.035(\text{Reliability})]$$

Where μ is consumer satisfaction with 1.702(constant), 0.7, 0.48 and 0.35 as gradients for empathy, assurance and reliability respectively. There are many inferences from this study for both researchers and marketers in Nepal. This study presents many of the real world guidance with respect to customer satisfaction and service quality as a whole and civil transportation industry in particular. This result lead to less confusion among marketers and researchers and also lead to more objective oriented studies rather than gap analysis or any other historic calculations. (Teel, 1983) Here is an attempt to quantify the relationship between two qualitative factors in transportation concern and more of further in depth studies can also give much clarity in this study.

Conclusion:

As result shows the consumer satisfaction is strongly correlated with service quality factors at different levels. As proposed in SERVQUAL method which is highly preferable to identify the relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction,

Nepal's transportation industry is also not an exemption. This study supports that a company engaging in services business, by carrying out all the possible roles which can promote the level of satisfaction to the consumers. As a result of in depth analysis and having a model for every factor of the service quality can give inner understandings of the customer satisfaction under different circumstances (Darely, 1985). Many other studies also propose the transaction specific model which is also suitable for better performance. But that may lead to complex understandings and difficult to implement in practical situations. (Oliver, 1981)

Further studies needs to be done in other services industries of Nepal which can benefit to have in depth understanding of customer satisfaction and service quality dimensions. Further, while it is likely that original studies could be gainfully learned by integrating study that deals with insolence creation, stability, and closure, totally too much of the reinforcements of our understanding of satisfaction, opportunities, and observations still breaks on investigation done in psychology or consumer behavior (Singh,J, 1990). In tallying, studies that integrate the fruitfulness of comparison-level theory.

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